

Table 1. BB reaction of rice varieties at Pantnagar in 1984 kharif.

SES score	Variety or elite strain
0	—
1	—
3	DV85, BJI, UPRB30, UPRB31, IET4141
5	Kinmaze, Tetep, IR29, IR43, IR50, IR54, UPRH300, RP633, RP633-9-8-1
7	IR8, Javal4, 70x45, IR22, IR23, IR38, IR42, IR48, IR52, UPRH137, RP633-519-1-1-1
9	IR1545-339-3-2, Kogyoku, Kuntlan, T(N) 11, Nagina 5, DR92, IR30, IR32, IR36, IR44, IR45, IR46, IR56, TKM9, Bala, Govind, Pusa 33, Saket 4, Ratna, Prasad, IR24, Pant Dhan 4, Jaya, T3, Tilakchand, UPRH93, UPRH130, UPRH153, UPRH166, UPRH216, UPRH245, UPRH246, UPRH247, CR167-7, CR200-788-3, AD9246, OR173-1-1, RP1036-35-2-5-1-1, PR103, Pusa 205-15-1, CR163-CRRP 56, CR75-93 Mut. 11-4, OR147-1-137, RP1575636-6-1, RP1775-243-719, OR79-21, SKL6, OR131-5-8, HPU804, BPT1235, BIET236, AAU49-31-2, RP79-104, UPR254-24-1-1, UPK10344-2, NDR301, NDR302, KR1047, PAU4056-53-5, NSRP II Late, BAU4040-1, UPR81-44, BK670, NRL326-3, Rasi, Camposelak, TKM6, RW9-9, RP825-24-9-1, RP975-28-4-2, LZN, IR20, Sayaphal, RP2151-40-1, OR164-5, RP1667-301-1196-1562, RP1451-17124319

from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program, popular high yielding varieties from Uttar Pradesh, and some resistant lines from hill germplasm maintained at Pantnagar.

The entries were sown 10 Jul 1984 and transplanted 30 Jul; each was in 2 rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Recommended fertilizers and irrigation were applied and plots were kept weed free. Forty-five days after transplanting, five plants in each row were clip-inoculated with naturally occurring inoculum. Disease reaction was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

Govind and Prasad, which were bred from TKM6 at Pantnagar and possess the *Xa 4* gene for resistance to BB, had susceptible reaction (Table 1). This indicates that a new race of the BB pathogen that will break down resistance conferred by the *Xa 4* gene may have evolved (Table 2). The lines BJI, DV85, UPRB30, UPRB31, and IET4141 were resistant. BJI and

Table 2. BB reaction of some resistant rices at Pantnagar, 1982-84.

Variety	Gene for resistance	BB reaction (0-9) ^a		
		1982	1983	1984
TKM6	<i>Xa 4</i>	3	3	9
Govind	<i>Xa 4</i>	3	5	9
Prasad	<i>Xa 4</i>	5	5	9
IR20	<i>Xa 4</i>	3	5	9
IR22	<i>Xa 4</i>	5	7	7
BJI	<i>xa 5</i>	3	3	3
IET4141	<i>xa 5</i>	3	3	3
DV85	<i>xa 5 + Xa 7</i>	3	3	3
Pant Dhan-4	not known	5	5	9
UPRB30	-do-	3	3	3
UPRB31	-do-	3	3	3
TN1	No gene	9	9	9

^a Scored by SES.

IET4141 have the *xa 5* gene for resistance and DV85 has *xa 5* and *Xa 7* genes. These sources of resistance appeared to be the only reliable sources among rices adapted to Pantnagar conditions. They are being used in the breeding program. *ℳ*

Effect of bulky organic manures on sheath blight (ShB)

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ShB is an important rice disease in Andhra Pradesh. Applying bulky organic manures has been reported to enhance soil microbiological activity, which may increase ShB. We evaluated the effect of organic manure on ShB incidence at ARS in 1983 kharif.

Different amounts of 5 bulky organic manures (see table) were incorporated 15 d before transplanting. Fertilizer application was adjusted to 100-30-30 kg NPK/ha. The experiment was in a randomized block design with four replications. Highly ShB-susceptible MTU6024 was planted in 5.8- × 3.4-m plots at 20- × 1km spacing. Natural disease incidence was recorded at dough Stage.

Incorporating neem cake, castor cake, rice straw, green leaf (*Gliricidia*

Effect of bulky organic manures on ShB and rice yield,^a Maruteru, India.

Manure	Dosage/ha	Disease index (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Neem cake	250 kg	68	4.4	6.4
Neem cake	500 kg	69	4.5	6.5
Castor cake	250 kg	65	4.7	6.8
Castor cake	500 kg	68	4.9	6.4
Rice straw	2t	67	4.6	6.5
Rice straw	6t	66	4.1	6.5
Green leaf	2t	69	4.8	7.2
Green leaf	8t	66	4.8	7.2
Farmyard manure	8t	67	4.4	7.3
Control	—	67	4.5	7.3
F test		ns	s	ns
CD@ 5%		—	0.3	—
CV%		6.2	5.8	8.9

^a ns = nonsignificant, s = significant.

muculatu), or farmyard manure did not affect ShB incidence. Grain yields, however, differed significantly among

the treatments. Straw yields were similar. Yield variations were attributed to reasons other than ShB incidence. *ℳ*

Maize — a new host of rice gall dwarf virus (GDV)

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We studied the host range of GDV in

1983 in Guangdong Province, China. Eight plant species grown in pots were confined with 1-5 viruliferous zigzag leafhoppers *Recilia dorsalis* Motsch per plant until the vector died (34 d). Maize plants also were inoculated with green leafhopper *Nephotettix cincticeps*. Disease symptoms developed 15-25 d after inoculation. Plants without symptoms were observed for 5-6 mo.

GDV infected wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), oat (*Avena sativa*), wild rice (*Oryza rufipogon*), Japanese grass (*Alopecurus aequalis*), and maize (*Zea mays*). Small galls developed on field grass (*Leptochloa chinensis*), but further confirmation is needed. *Echinochloa crus-galli* and *Leersia hexandra* did not have virus symptoms (see table).

Maize is a new host of GDV. Both zigzag and green leafhoppers

Host range of GDV in Guangdong, China, 1983.^a

Host	Zigzag leafhopper per plant	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (no.)
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	1	17	2
<i>Avena sativa</i>	1	15	3
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	4	6	3
<i>Alopecurus aequalis</i>	5	3	2
	3	12	1
<i>Zea mays</i>	7	5	1
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	3	5	small galls
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	3	5	0
	3	5	0
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	1	15	0

^a*Nephotettix cincticeps* were used to inoculate the virus.

transmitted GDV to maize. Symptoms developed 28 d after inoculation. Small, light green galls appeared on the leaf veins, enlarged, and became waxy white. Some galls formed vein swellings up to

1.5 cm long and 0.25 cm wide. Stunting was not serious. The results were confirmed when rice plants exhibited typical symptoms after back-inoculation. *J*

Rice diseases on the Godavari Delta

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We surveyed rice disease status in 1983 rabi, 1984 kharif, and 1984 rabi in East

and West Godavari Districts. Surveyors visited 69 villages and talked with 86 farmers in West Godavari, and visited 31 villages and talked with 35 farmers in East Godavari.

- Blast (BI), which only occurs in rabi, sheath blight (ShB), and

bacterial blight were major diseases, and caused substantial yield losses.

- Tungro (RTV) occurs sporadically, but southern coastal districts had RTV epidemics in 1984 kharif.
- IR50 is highly susceptible to BI. Applying heavy N doses (60-140 kg N/ha) increased BI disease seventy. Rabi varieties BPT1235 and IR62 have BI resistance (see table).
- Stem rot caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, brown spot caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and sheath rot caused by *Acrocyldrium oryzae* were sometimes observed, but caused negligible losses. *J*

Disease incidence^a on different rices in Andhra Pradesh, India, 1983-84.

Variety	Disease incidence				
	Bacterial blight	Blast	Tungro	Sheath blight	Stem rot
			<i>Rabi</i>		
IR50	–	VS	–	M	–
IET1444	M	–	S	–	SL
BPT1235	SL	SL	M	S	–
IR62	–	M	–	S	–
RP6-17	–	SL	M	–	SL
Prabhat	–	–	SL	–	–
IR36	–	M	–	–	–
Mahsuri	–	–	–	–	–
MTU5 249	–	–	–	M	–
			<i>Kharif</i>		
MTU7029	SL	–	–	S	–
MTU5249	–	–	–	–	M
MTU4870	–	–	–	M	–
MTU2077	M	–	–	M	–
MTU2067	M	–	–	M	–
RP6-17	–	–	–	M	–
MTU6024	SL	–	–	M	–
IR42	SL	–	–	–	–
Jaya	SL	–	–	–	–
Mahsuri	SL	–	–	–	–
Swarna Mahsuri	SL	–	–	–	–
IR62	M	–	–	S	–

^a SL = slight, M = moderate, S = severe, VS = very severe.

BR3 reaction to multiple disease infection

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Rice fields often are infected by more than one disease. We evaluated BR3 under multiple disease infection. BR3 seedlings were transplanted in 48 rows of 10 hills each. The field received the recommended 80-60-40 kg NPK/ha.